

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

Daniel Linhares Lim-Apo

¹University of Brasília (UnB), Department of Computer Science, Brasília, DF, Brazil
E-mail: daniel.unb@sede.com.br, ednacanedo@unb.br

Table 1. PICOC terms

PICOC	Keywords	Related Words
Population	textual data, sensitive text	unstructured text, natural language data, corpora, text, private data, confidential document, textual dataset, personal text data, privacy-sensitive textual corpora
Intervention	privacy-preserving techniques, semantic similarity, rarity detection	privacy protection, anonymization, pseudonymization, differential privacy, privacy-enhancing, re-identification, AI, data science, data analytics, machine learning, artificial intelligence, AI model, GPT, BERT, agent, predictive modeling, statistical modeling, natural language processing, NLP, language model, transformer model, sentence similarity, document similarity, semantic matching, text similarity, cosine similarity, embedding similarity, vector similarity, semantic distance, similarity metrics, lexical similarity, similarity detection rare word, low-frequency term, outlier, anomaly, rare entity, statistical rarity, frequency analysis
Comparison	<i>Not applicable</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>
Outcome	privacy in textual data analysis, protection of sensitive content, detection of semantic structure and rare or distinctive patterns	interpretability, analytical utility, semantic richness, text clustering, topic modeling, document classification, privacy protection, risk mitigation, data anonymization, balance between utility and privacy, privacy-utility trade-off, knowledge extraction, meaning preservation
Context	natural language processing, ethical AI, information retrieval	privacy in AI, responsible AI, legal NLP, AI agents, autonomous agents, conversational AI, large language models, LLM, foundation models, data science.